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Gap Analysis and Strategic Opportunities for the European Cloud-Edge-IoT Market

White paper

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	3
2. Demand for CEI & Technology Requirements in the Computing Continuum	4
2.1 Demand for CEI	4
2.2 Technology Requirements.....	4
3. Key Market Gaps.....	8
3.1 Edge Platforms and Data Management.....	8
3.2 Analytics and AI.....	8
3.3 Integration	9
3.4 Trust and Security.....	10
3.5 Connectivity and Communication.....	10
3.6 Digital Twins.....	11
3.7 Devices	11
3.8 Other Ecosystem Gaps	12
3.9 Other Key Gaps.....	12
4. Recommendations.....	14
Sources.....	15

List of Figures

Figure 1. Benefits of Edge Computing (UNLOCK-CEI Survey, March 2023)	5
Figure 2. Planned Location of Edge Resources by Industry (UNLOCK-CEI Survey, March 2023)	6
Figure 3. Key Technologies Associated with CEI Projects (UNLOCK-CEI Survey, March 2023)	7

1. Introduction

The Cloud, Edge and IoT (CEI) computing continuum is crucial to Europe's technological landscape, offering significant benefits to businesses, governments, and society. By leveraging IoT data, distributed computing power, advanced 5G networks, AI, automation, and other technologies, CEI promises to transform European operations. To foster CEI development, the European Commission (EC) supports various research projects to address technological gaps, enabling Europe to harness these innovations and lead future tech markets.

The European normative context and initiatives for the computing continuum reflect the region's commitment to advancing the CEI landscape. The EC has enacted various regulatory frameworks and initiatives to support this development, such as the European Data Strategy¹ and the Digital Europe Programme.² These frameworks aim to create a single market for data, fostering data sharing across sectors and borders to enhance European competitiveness and sovereignty while ensuring data privacy and security. In fostering a single market for data, these initiatives also aim to investigate and evaluate demand-side drivers and challenges, technological innovations, and business opportunities for CEI's market growth to build a robust, secure, and competitive European CEI ecosystem. These efforts collectively aim to strengthen Europe's position in the global digital economy by developing next-generation cloud and edge infrastructures.

Among the initiatives focusing on unlocking CEI demand-side potential and identifying gaps is the EU-funded project UNLOCK-CEI, part of the EUCloudEdgeIoT umbrella initiative.³ This document presents the results of our analysis carried out under this project.

To carry out such an analysis, 700 European enterprises were surveyed, and in-depth interviews with ecosystem participants and CEI solution developers were conducted, complemented by additional desk research.⁴ This research provides an overview of key lessons learned about CEI adoption in Europe and analyses current gaps between market demands and availability, outlining key challenges and barriers to adoption. Market gaps are categorised and evaluated based on their importance and the current efforts to address them, and recommendations for future actions are provided.

1 See <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/strategy-data>.

2 See <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32022R2065>.

3 See <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/>

4 See respectively, D1.1 Cloud-Edge-IoT Demand Landscape (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7821330>); D1.2 Updated report of CEI demand landscape (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8107103>); D1.3 Cloud-Edge-IoT Demand Landscape: CEI Gap Analysis and Opportunities (<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12773512>).

2. Demand for CEI & Technology Requirements in the Computing Continuum

The development of the CEI computing continuum is dependent upon the development of a range of supporting technologies, which is also a key driver of demand for those technologies. The UNLOCK-CEI survey findings showcase the use and planned adoption of these technologies for improved efficiency, data management, and real-time analytics, alongside the crucial role of 5G, big data, and AI in enhancing CEI solutions.

2.1 Demand for CEI

The CEI computing continuum, which integrates IoT sensors and devices with cloud and edge computing resources, is widely adopted across Europe. Research shows strong interest in and demand for CEI solutions, with familiarity and usage varying by technology. The UNLOCK-CEI survey revealed that 50% of respondents are using IoT, and another 22% plan to do so within two years, citing benefits such as improved efficiency, better customer experience, decision-making, and product quality. IoT is seen as strategically important or transformational by 50% of respondents, indicating its significance in various business activities.

To harness these benefits, organisations need end-to-end solutions connecting IoT devices to computing resources and applications, often located in the cloud. Cloud computing, already widely used for IT functions, is now powering IoT solutions, with 72% of survey respondents using cloud services and 18% planning to do so within two years. For IoT projects, 29% already use cloud services, and another 33% plan to, highlighting the cloud's role in managing distributed devices and data analysis.

Edge computing, crucial for real-time data analysis and advanced automation, is the least mature component of the CEI continuum. It supports innovative use cases by processing data close to the source, which is essential for applications requiring real-time control and large data volumes. The survey indicated that only 29% of respondents currently use edge computing, with 30% planning to adopt it within two years. Despite challenges such as a lack of tools and standards, awareness and anticipation of edge computing needs remain high.

2.2 Technology Requirements

CEI solutions comprise numerous technology components, including devices with built-in computing capabilities and sensors for data collection. Depending on specific requirements and available resources, these devices may perform initial data analysis before transmitting it over a network connection to a gateway, edge node, or directly to the cloud. In some scenarios, edge computing resources are strategically positioned closer to the devices, facilitating real-time data processing, automation, and control of remote devices through applications and analytical models. This architecture ensures efficient data management and operational effectiveness.

Edge Requirements

As CEI solutions evolve, offering more functionality and automation, the strategic placement of computing resources at the edge becomes crucial. The UNLOCK-CEI survey identified several key benefits of edge computing, with 42% of respondents emphasising security and compliance by minimising data travel. Another significant benefit is reducing data volumes sent to the cloud, cited by 38%, which lowers network costs and enhances efficiency. Furthermore, 36% of respondents highlighted the importance of edge computing for achieving very low latency, which is essential for applications requiring real-time responses, such as automated machinery control.

Figure 1. Benefits of Edge Computing (UNLOCK-CEI Survey, March 2023)

Interviews with end users and vendors corroborate these findings, underscoring the importance of edge computing for maintaining low latency and reliable connectivity, especially in sectors like agriculture with limited network infrastructure. Edge computing resources can be deployed in various contexts: within enterprise data centres (enterprise edge), at industrial sites like factories and ports (operations edge), co-located with telecom infrastructure (telco edge), or directly on devices such as drones and vehicles (device edge).

Overall, respondents indicated significant adoption plans for different edge computing categories – from telco edge to device edge, “on-premises” category merging enterprise and operations edge and “distributed cloud edge,” with cloud providers delivering edge infrastructure using their platforms and services. In particular, interviews highlighted on-premises and on-devices as the most common edge locations across various vertical sectors. For example, edge computing on vehicles was crucial for advanced features like driver fatigue detection using computer vision. Manufacturers aimed to enable self-optimisation by incorporating edge computing into their products. In port operations, both on-premises and on-device edge solutions were commonly discussed.

Question: Where do you expect to locate edge resources in the next two years? [Choose all that apply]
 n=500 (Base: Edge users or planners)

Figure 2. Planned Location of Edge Resources by Industry (UNLOCK-CEI Survey, March 2023)

Complementary Technologies

CEI solutions are developing alongside rapid technological innovation, integrating various technologies tailored to individual use cases. The survey identified 5G as the most crucial technology for CEI plans, with frequent mentions in interviews. For transportation, 5G enables significant data transfer for smart vehicles, while in agriculture, automated machinery benefits from enhanced network coverage, including Long Term Evolution (LTE) and satellite systems. Industry discussions also highlighted interest in private 5G networks for locations like manufacturing plants, ports, and healthcare facilities. Big data and analytics were the second most mentioned technologies, requiring sophisticated strategies and tools to manage, analyse, and utilise data from CEI solutions. Data management increasingly leverages both classical analytics and artificial intelligence. Interviews emphasised the role of AI and analytics in pre-processing data, reducing network data volumes, and enabling real-time analysis for alerts and automation. While AI appeared lower in the survey results, its relevance has likely increased significantly since the survey was conducted due to the rise of generative AI technologies like ChatGPT.

Question: Which of the following technologies are important parts of your Cloud, Edge and IoT plans? [Choose all that apply]
n=700 (Base: all respondents)

Figure 3. Key Technologies Associated with CEI Projects (UNLOCK-CEI Survey, March 2023)

Additional technologies such as digital twins, autonomous vehicles, robotics, virtual reality (VR), and augmented reality (AR) are also integral to some CEI solutions. Each use case determines the specific technologies and services required, creating unique architectural needs. For instance, fleet management solutions often rely on cloud computing, while agricultural machinery automation and port operations demand substantial edge computing capabilities. Despite the varying requirements, a combination of edge and cloud resources is typically employed to optimise performance and meet the specific needs of each application.

3. Key Market Gaps

Key market gaps regarding the deployment of CEI technologies were identified and separated into categories reflecting the computing continuum building blocks shown above. The gaps vary by type, with some being purely technology gaps, while others are gaps in standards, organisational readiness, legal and policy domains, and other ecosystem issues.

3.1 Edge Platforms and Data Management

Several essential components of the computing continuum relate to the data management process, such as data pipelines, brokering, storage, and orchestration software. Key gaps identified in these areas include:

- 🔗 **Complex and fragmented edge software solutions:** managing edge devices and distributed applications is a complex task, requiring multiple modules and vendors, making integration challenging. This was noted by manufacturers, port operators, open-source developers, and analytics providers.
- 🔗 **Incompatible proprietary platforms:** many vendors offer proprietary edge platforms that do not integrate well with others, leading to vendor lock-in.
- 🔗 **Need for open standards and open-source software:** open-source software and standards for edge management are beneficial, though the market remains fragmented.
- 🔗 **Unprepared organisations for data management and governance:** many organisations have isolated data silos and resist sharing data, needing upgraded systems and strategies for effective data utilisation.
- 🔗 **Too many (Operational Technology) OT data protocols:** the existence of numerous incompatible OT data protocols complicates edge solutions, requiring simplification and integration.
- 🔗 **Edge orchestration and automation tools:** consistent orchestration and automation tools are needed as workloads shift between cloud and edge.
- 🔗 **Common language and taxonomy:** inconsistent terminology and taxonomies around edge software cause market confusion.
- 🔗 **Development of device-edge applications:** OEMs struggle to find clear and easy solutions for deploying connected intelligence on their products, often developing their own platforms.

Key initiatives addressing these gaps include:

- 🔗 **EUCloudEdgeIoT initiative and MetaOS projects:** these are tackling challenges in edge platforms and management.
- 🔗 **Linux Foundation's LF Edge initiative:** progress has been made with technologies like EdgeX Foundry, though the market is still maturing and lacks standard consolidation.

To overcome these gaps, the CEI ecosystem should focus on harmonising standards and ontologies, supporting open-source projects, and fostering innovation and development in both vertical solutions and horizontal technologies.

3.2 Analytics and AI

Analytics, crucial for CEI solutions, operates both in the cloud and at the edge. Cloud-based analytics handles large-scale, batch, and real-time data, while edge analytics pre-processes data to reduce network traffic and storage demands, enabling faster real-time assessments. However, significant challenges exist:

- ☁ **Managing analytics and AI at the edge:** unlike mature cloud-based analytics, edge analytics is nascent and complex. It involves managing the lifecycle of numerous models across diverse devices, implementing them on resource-constrained devices, and integrating them with real-time data and equipment.
- ☁ **Data quality:** companies struggle with poor data quality, necessitating robust data management and cleaning strategies. An IDC survey highlighted data quality as the top challenge in sharing industrial IoT data in Germany.⁵
- ☁ **AI skills shortage:** the demand for AI and analytics skills surpasses supply, making it essential for CEI solution providers to make these technologies more accessible.

The EU supports projects that build CEI solutions, fostering the development of technical solutions and expertise to tackle analytics and AI challenges and address these gaps. The EU's new AI Act establishes a legal framework for AI use, adopting a risk-based approach where higher-risk AI systems face stricter regulations. Given the critical nature of IoT and CEI, these systems are likely subject to stringent safety standards.⁶

Further AI guidance will be necessary as technology and use cases evolve. Support for developing AI expertise and a skilled workforce will be crucial for advancing European leadership in AI-driven CEI solutions.

3.3 Integration

Integration poses significant challenges for CEI solutions development and deployment. Despite ongoing efforts, several key market gaps persist:

- ☁ **Fragmented ecosystem:** The market is divided into numerous use cases, each requiring different sensors, devices, architectures, and other components, necessitating unique value chains and solutions for each use case.
- ☁ **Incompatible protocols and standards:** Numerous incompatible protocols and standards, particularly in OT environments, complicate integration. The fragmentation and nascent status of edge environments, along with legacy OT systems, exacerbate this issue, making integration complex.
- ☁ **Retrofitting older equipment:** Integrating older industrial equipment into modern CEI solutions is challenging due to security risks, technical limitations, and legal or contractual constraints.
- ☁ **Need for repeatable end-to-end solutions:** Many organisations cannot afford custom solutions and require scalable, repeatable end-to-end solutions that simplify integration and reduce costs.

Several initiatives are underway to tackle these integration challenges:

- ☁ **Development of end-to-end solutions:** Companies are creating repeatable solutions for various use cases to simplify integration and reduce costs.
- ☁ **Establishment of technical solutions:** Efforts are being made to develop horizontal technical solutions that can be applied across multiple use cases.
- ☁ **Standards development:** Organizations like the Linux Foundation's LF Edge, 3GPP, the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C), and the Industry IoT Consortium (IIC) are working to establish common standards.

Continued support is needed to develop commercial end-to-end solutions for specific use cases and harmonise standards in OT, edge orchestration, and software stacks for smart meters or (Electric Vehicle) EV chargers.

5 IDC, "Industrial Internet of Things Survey in Germany/DACH", September 2023.

6 See https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:L_202401689.

3.4 Trust and Security

Security remains a top challenge for European companies adopting CEI solutions, with the March 2023 UNLOCK CEI survey identifying it as one of the top barriers to cloud, edge, and IoT adoption. Key security gaps include:

- 🔒 **Securing end devices:** Edge devices are vulnerable due to their distributed nature and limited security measures, necessitating robust protocols, encryption, and access controls.
- 🔒 **Physical tampering and attacks:** Edge devices in accessible locations are at risk of tampering and physical attacks.
- 🔒 **Connecting legacy equipment:** Integrating new solutions with older technology can introduce security vulnerabilities, technical challenges, and legal constraints.
- 🔒 **OT cybersecurity expertise:** OT departments need specialised cybersecurity training, as merging with IT introduces new security demands.
- 🔒 **Managing edge device updates:** Security updates, patches, and configurations for numerous edge devices and applications are complex to manage.
- 🔒 **Preserving privacy:** IoT devices collecting vast amounts of data can inadvertently capture private information, requiring clear methodologies and legal frameworks for compliance.
- 🔒 **Cybersecurity policies and requirements:** Evolving cybersecurity challenges in the CEI continuum necessitate ongoing policy and legal adjustments.
- 🔒 **Ethical use of AI:** Rapid AI development requires continuous attention to ethical, legal, and safety issues, ensuring AI is used responsibly, especially in sensitive areas like healthcare.

Efforts to address these security challenges include:

- 🔒 **ENISA:** The European Union Agency for Cybersecurity supports the development of cybersecurity practices and technologies across the EU, offering guidelines for managing IoT and smart infrastructure security.
- 🔒 **EU Cybersecurity Policies:** These include the GDPR, the Cybersecurity Act strengthening ENISA, and the proposed Cyber Resilience Act, which aims to standardise IoT device security with mandatory requirements for manufacturers and retailers.
- 🔒 **EU Internet of Things Policy and CEI Initiatives:** Cooperation with industry and academia under Horizon Europe funds the development of secure CEI technologies and solutions.

Continued focus on security and trust is crucial as the CEI continuum evolves. Europe's leadership in security can foster a robust CEI industry meeting high standards. ENISA and the EU should support further development of best practices, certifications, and compliance to address emerging market needs, ensuring the European CEI ecosystem adheres to stringent security norms.

3.5 Connectivity and Communication

In regard to connectivity, several market gaps emerged:

- 🔒 **Rural and remote coverage:** Many rural and remote areas lack 5G, LPWAN, and other networks, impacting industries like agriculture. A mix of terrestrial and non-terrestrial (satellite) networks is needed.
- 🔒 **5G network development:** 5G networks are not yet fully developed across Europe, and 5G core networks, essential for ultra-low latency, are still not widely used.
- 🔒 **Private 5G solutions:** Private 5G networks can fill gaps in public 5G services, enabling advanced edge-IoT use cases, but these are still in their early stages.
- 🔒 **Low-Earth orbiting (LEO) satellite systems:** While satellite connectivity is advancing rapidly, particularly with services like SpaceX's Starlink, CEI use cases for satellite services are still nascent, and European companies lag behind.

Several initiatives are addressing these connectivity challenges:

- ☁ **3GPP Standards:** The 3GPP coordinates standards for cellular networks, including 5G, LPWAN, and satellite connectivity.
- ☁ **European Commission support:** Programs like the 5G Infrastructure Public-Private Partnership (5G PPP) and spectrum harmonisation efforts aim to accelerate 5G deployment, including in rural areas.
- ☁ **Private 5G spectrum:** Some EU Member States have allocated spectrum for private 5G networks.
- ☁ **EU Space Programme:** This includes the CASSINI Initiative, supporting entrepreneurs and SMEs in the space industry with a €1 billion seed and growth fund.
- ☁ **5G core network deployment:** Mobile operators in Europe are beginning to deploy 5G core networks for advanced capabilities.
- ☁ **Satellite connectivity initiatives:** European companies like Sateliot and Telefónica are testing IoT device connectivity across terrestrial and LEO satellite networks.

Additional efforts could include reserving more spectrum for private network usage and further EU initiatives to support European satellite IoT connectivity.

3.6 Digital Twins

Digital twins were periodically mentioned as a key tool for CEI solutions during research interviews. While few major challenges were highlighted, the field is still in its early stages.

Digital twins will require further investment and innovation, with market forces expected to drive much of the development. Further research specifically focused on digital twins could uncover key gaps and identify initiatives to address them.

3.7 Devices

Several key gaps in the IoT device market emerged:

- ☁ **Device design skills:** Many organisations lack the skills required to design custom IoT devices tailored to specific use cases, often needing assistance or simpler solutions.
- ☁ **5G-ready devices:** Few operations technology and equipment vendors have integrated 5G connectivity into their devices, complicating retrofitting efforts.
- ☁ **Affordable 5G modules:** 5G connectivity modules remain expensive and power-hungry compared to other modules.

The market is beginning to address these challenges. Research and development efforts are leading to more off-the-shelf devices, reducing the need for custom development. As demand for 5G connectivity grows, more equipment manufacturers are expected to integrate 5G into their devices. Additionally, the 3GPP has introduced standards for “reduced capability” 5G RedCap, enabling the production of more affordable, less power-intensive devices.

Further efforts to simplify the CEI continuum will likely drive demand and help address remaining device gaps. Initiatives could include:

- ☁ **Training and education:** Providing resources and programs to enhance device design skills within organisations.
- ☁ **Incentives for manufacturers:** Offering incentives for equipment manufacturers to integrate 5G connectivity into their products.
- ☁ **Research and innovation grants:** Funding to support the development of affordable and efficient 5G modules.

- ☁ **Collaboration and standardisation:** Promoting collaboration between industry players and standardisation bodies to ensure interoperability and reduce complexity.

By focusing on these areas, the IoT device market can overcome current gaps and better support the CEI continuum.

3.8 Other Ecosystem Gaps

Several critical gaps exist outside previously discussed categories, which, if unaddressed, may hinder development:

- ☁ **Local suppliers and digital sovereignty:** Companies prefer vendors and solutions based in Europe for latency, local support, and digital sovereignty.
- ☁ **Data-sharing initiatives / Data Spaces:** Many use cases require data sharing across the value chain, such as in the food and pharmaceutical industries. Platforms and marketplaces for secure data exchange are needed.
- ☁ **Commercialization and scale:** European companies risk falling behind global players despite participating in CEI development if they fail to achieve scale and widespread adoption.
- ☁ **Open-source solutions:** Open-source projects are essential for addressing fragmentation, challenging dominant outside players, and ensuring security and sovereignty.

Several European policy initiatives and private-sector efforts are addressing these gaps:

- ☁ **Local suppliers and digital sovereignty:** The EU supports local businesses through initiatives like the EUCloudEdgeIoT and MetaOS projects despite losing cloud services market share to dominant hyperscalers.
- ☁ **Data-sharing initiatives:** The EU's Common European Data Spaces, part of the European Strategy for Data, funds industry-specific data spaces for secure data exchange. Platforms like SIMPL and organisations like the International Data Sharing Association (IDSA) and Gaia-X are key players in this effort.
- ☁ **Commercialisation and scale:** Horizon Europe funds innovation projects to help develop commercially viable CEI solutions. Various policies aim to create a fertile ground for global leaders in CEI technologies.

Digital sovereignty and data spaces will take years to develop and require ongoing support. The EU should continue funding, open calls, and policy initiatives to address these and related issues, ensuring the successful development of a robust CEI ecosystem.

3.9 Other Key Gaps

The market gaps above are being addressed by market forces, public policies, standards bodies, industry consortia, and other initiatives. However, several key gaps still require further attention. Policy-makers and other stakeholders should consider focusing on the following areas:

- ☁ **Edge orchestration tools:** There is a need for enhancement in terms of interoperability, security and automation for effective management of distributed solutions. Continued support is needed for projects like MetaOS, LF Edge, and industry efforts to enable the commercialization and scaling of distributed edge solutions.
- ☁ **Edge standards:** Simplification and harmonisation of edge standards are necessary to avoid confusion and lock-in from competing standards and proprietary systems, reducing costs and risks.
- ☁ **Edge platforms for OEMs:** Manufacturers need easier access to tools that accelerate the time to market for smart connected products.

- ☁ **CEI and complementary skills:** There is a need for upskilling and reskilling in terms of CEI technologies and in relation to complementary technologies such as AI.
- ☁ **Trust and security:** An ongoing focus on trust and security is crucial to minimising and mitigating risks in the rapidly developing CEI space.
- ☁ **Connectivity and 5G networks:** Public 5G network coverage remains incomplete, and advanced 5G services are slow to arrive. Support for the nascent private 5G network market and increased spectrum availability can enhance public and private 5G network coverage and services.
- ☁ **Non-terrestrial networks:** European policy support is likely needed to help European companies compete in the satellite connectivity market, where Starlink currently has a significant lead.
- ☁ **Industry-specific use cases:** Because the continuum is fragmented across hundreds of use cases, much work is needed to enable European organisations to leverage these technologies for their unique purposes. Continued support from research organisations and public funding is necessary to help solution providers commercialise industry-specific use cases and achieve scale.
- ☁ **Commercialisation and scale:** European companies will need to scale aggressively in a fiercely competitive global market through large-scale industry policy. Policies and support are needed to help European companies aggressively scale CEI solutions and technologies in the global market after early-stage development and productisation.
- ☁ **Concrete business cases: Companies** need justified business cases to adopt edge, and ROI is unclear.

4. Recommendations

Based on the analysis of key market gaps provided above, some key recommendations for addressing such gaps can be formulated, including highlighting several areas requiring additional initiatives. Policy-makers and other stakeholders, such as standards bodies and research organisations, should consider the following efforts:

- ☁ **Support innovation in CEI technologies with an industry-specific focus:** Continued investment in fragmented CEI markets is essential to address diverse use cases, enhance capabilities, and move solutions towards commercial feasibility.
- ☁ **Establish common open standards:** Reducing market confusion and project costs through open standards will enable companies to scale solutions more quickly. Harmonisation efforts are needed to ensure interoperability and seamless integration.
- ☁ **Promote open-source technologies as a strategic asset:** Open-source technologies can prevent market dominance by proprietary suppliers, ensuring Europe's digital sovereignty and competitive edge. Open-source solutions should adhere to standardised protocols for interoperability.
- ☁ **Accelerate upskilling and reskilling across the computing continuum:** Boost education in relevant fields, provide funding for innovation, and implement new approaches like micro-training and joint industry-research short courses to accelerate workforce reskilling and upskilling.
- ☁ **Support scaling from medium to large markets:** Policies are needed to accelerate the growth of commercialised CEI businesses toward global success. Promote international collaboration and develop global standards to ensure the compatibility of European solutions worldwide. In particular, it is recommended that international bodies work with each other to develop global standards and protocols, ensuring European solutions are compatible worldwide.
- ☁ **Build a comprehensive legal and policy framework:** Provide further guidance on the ethics and safety of AI in the continuum while balancing legal clarity with flexibility, speed, and global competitiveness.
- ☁ **Balance risk mitigation with innovation:** Implement policies that mitigate risks, especially in cybersecurity and privacy, without stifling innovation. A balanced approach will maintain European companies' competitiveness.
- ☁ **Enhance data privacy and security:** Enforce robust data protection and cybersecurity regulations to ensure user trust. Extend collaboration within the ecosystem to engage industry experts, technology providers, and consumer advocacy groups, ensuring practical and effective regulations.

By focusing on these areas, policymakers and stakeholders can address critical market gaps and support the development and scaling of CEI solutions in Europe. As further research within UNLOCK-CEI progresses, these gaps and opportunities will be continuously evaluated and updated. As such, the project will continue to develop and share updated insights through future publications and presentations.

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